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A novel laboratory method for the retrieval of the soil water retention curve from shortwave infrared reflectance

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ABSTRACT

The soil water retention curve (SWRC) is an essential soil property that relates soil water content and matric potential. It plays a crucial role in soil water dynamics and the understanding of various hydrological phenomena at the land surface, including infiltration, runoff, evaporation, and energy exchange processes. In recent years, proximal sensing methods have shown great potential for retrieving this challenging-to-measure property from spectral reflectance. However, a physically-based approach is still lacking as current methods rely on empirical data-driven algorithms. Here we propose a novel physics-based laboratory method that, for the first time, enables direct estimation of the entire SWRC from saturated to dry using soil water content/reflectance data pairs within the shortwave infrared domain. The main hypothesis underlying the new method is that soil optical properties not only vary with soil water content but also with the pore scale distribution of capillary and adsorbed soil water. For evaluation, retrieved soil water retention curves of 21 soils that vastly differ in physical and hydraulic properties were compared to direct measurements. The results suggest that the new method is a rapid and efficient alternative to established laboratory measurement methods.

1. Introduction

Partitioning of infiltration and evaporation fluxes at the land surface and accurate quantification of mass and energy exchange processes between the soil and atmosphere at different spatial scales requires the knowledge of soil hydraulic properties (i.e., water retention and hydraulic conductivity curves). Determination of the water balance at the land-atmosphere boundary strongly depends on the accurate characterization of soil hydraulic properties at the appropriate process scale (Mohanty, 2013; Montzka et al., 2017).

The soil water retention curve describes the soil water content (θ), i.e., the volume of water per volume of soil under equilibrium at a given matric potential (h). The SWRC is an essential hydrologic property related to the size distribution and geometry of the soil pore space. Hence, it is strongly affected by soil structure, texture, and soil constituents such as organic matter and clay minerals (Tuller and Or, 2005).

Measuring the SWRC with standard laboratory methods is laborious.

Measured θ - h pairs are often fragmentary and commonly comprise only a few measurements over the soil water content range of interest. These methods include the hanging water column (Dane and Hopmans, 2002), the Richards' pressure plate apparatus and Tempe cells (Dane and Hopmans, 2002), the chilled mirror dewpoint technique (Gee et al., 1992; Arthur et al., 2014), long column (Dane et al., 1992), and suction table (Romano et al., 2002) techniques.

Proximal and remote sensing techniques have received considerable attention in recent years as rapid and cost-efficient methods for the quantification of soil attributes at various scales. In particular, soil reflectance spectra in the optical domain (300–2500 nm) have been used to retrieve soil mineralogy and chemical composition (Omran, 2017; Coblinski et al., 2021; Mendes et al., 2021), soil organic matter content (Leue et al., 2017; Hong et al., 2018; Tziolas et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2021), soil particle size distribution (Bänninger et al., 2006; Hermansen et al., 2017; Sadeghi et al., 2018; Norouzi et al., 2021), the mineral fines to organic carbon ratio (Hermansen et al., 2016), and soil water content

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(Lobell and Asner, 2002; Sadeghi et al., 2015; Bablet et al., 2018; Tian et al., 2021, Dupiau et al., 2022). These studies at small spatial scales are important as they can potentially build the foundation for satellite remote sensing of the corresponding soil property at larger scales. An example is the Optical TRapezoid Model (OPTRAM) for large scale mapping of soil water content (Sadeghi et al., 2017) and actual evapotranspiration (Mokhtari et al., 2023), which was developed based on the Sadeghi et al. (2015) laboratory-scale physical relationship between soil water content and shortwave infrared reflectance.

Past studies centered around proximal and remote sensing of soil hydraulic functions mainly rely on statistical relationships, termed spectral transfer functions, that link a soil hydraulic parameter to dry soil reflectance spectra within the optical domain (Arslan et al., 2014; Babaeian et al., 2015a, 2015b; Pittaki-Chrysdonta et al., 2018; Blaschek et al., 2019; Pittaki et al., 2021). The accuracy of these relationships varies depending on the number and combination of the wavelengths considered for building the spectral transfer functions. Nonetheless, practical applications of most spectral transfer functions are often hampered by their very specific data requirements. While soil hydraulic properties can be effectively inferred from soil reflectance data using machine learning techniques, calibration of these models requires a large number of observations (Baumann et al., 2022).

There are also a few physics-based proximal sensing studies, which focus on the spatiotemporal estimation of soil water content rather than direct estimation of hydraulic properties. In this category of models, laboratory infiltration (Yu et al., 2021) or imbibition (Babaeian et al., 2021) experiments are designed to retrieve the water content at various locations using the proximally sensed signal. Depending on the wavelength of the signal, different algorithms can be applied to retrieve water content. To approximate the soil hydraulic properties, an optimization process is implemented to minimize the mismatch between the soil water content profiles determined from the proximally sensed signal and the soil water content simulated based on a governing flow equation such as Richards' (1931) equation. This optimization is done via perturbing the soil hydraulic parameters (Babaeian et al., 2021; Yu et al., 2021). Besides the inherent limitations of Richards' equation in describing the soil water flow (Vereecken et al., 2016) and the challenges associated with its inversion (Hopmans et al., 2002), these methods often require complex and expensive experimental setups.

This paper presents a new physically-based laboratory method for estimating the SWRC directly from the water content-dependent shortwave infrared (SWIR) soil reflectance spectra. The new method is based on inversion of the recently developed forward radiative transfer model of Norouzi et al. (2022), which connects soil reflectance in the SWIR region (i.e., 1400–2500 nm) to soil hydraulic properties. The new method relies only on water content-reflectance data pairs acquired during a soil drying experiment. It is computationally efficient as it directly derives the SWRC from the measurements without the need to invert a flow equation.

2. Theory

In this section, we briefly review the Norouzi et al. (2022) forward model for the soil water content-reflectance relationship. This model links the SWRC to the water content-reflectance relationship, and hence, enables retrieval of the SWRC from the water content-reflectance data pairs.

It is well-established that the optical properties of water bound to soil particles differ from that of pure water (Bach and Mauser, 1994; Philpot, 2010). Unlike for single-phase solid mixtures, in multi-phase mixtures (e.g., wet soil), the spectral reflectance of the mixture depends not only on the fraction of each constituent, but also on the structure or geometry of the wetting phase. Hence, the structural variations of soil water play a significant role in moisture-reflectance coupling, especially under wet and dry conditions (Tian et al., 2021).

Water is retained in soil in two forms; (i) capillary water filling the

space between soil particles, and (ii) adsorbed water consisting of a water film surrounding soil particles (Tuller et al., 1999; Norouzi et al., 2022). In general, capillary and adsorbed soil water coexist in partially saturated soils. When the soil dries, the capillary water recedes into the pore corners. Beyond a certain texture-dependent matric potential threshold, the retained water mainly exists as adsorbed water films.

Norouzi et al. (2022) hypothesized that the optical properties of wet soils significantly vary not only with soil water content, but also with the soil water structure around soil particles. To relate soil water content and reflectance spectra in the SWIR range, they relied on the Kubelka-Munk (KM) two-flux model (Kubelka and Munk, 1931). The KM model for an optically thick layer yields the following equation for reflectance, R , of the material (Ciani et al., 2005; Thennadil, 2008):

$$R = 1 + \frac{k}{s} - \sqrt{\left(\frac{k}{s}\right)^2 + 2\frac{k}{s}} \quad (1)$$

where k (m^{-1}) and s (m^{-1}) are the light absorption and scattering coefficients, respectively, which are functions of the medium properties and the wavelength (λ). Eq. (1) can be rearranged to:

$$r = \frac{k}{s} = \frac{(1-R)^2}{2R} \quad (2)$$

where r is referred to as “transformed reflectance” (Sadeghi et al., 2015).

Building on the main hypothesis that optical properties of water at the soil surface are a function of water structure (i.e., adsorbed or capillary), Norouzi et al. (2022) proposed a new mixing model for the optical properties of dry soil particles and soil water. They considered separate absorption and scattering properties for capillary and adsorbed water and derived the following equation for modeling transformed reflectance as a function of the capillary and adsorbed soil water components:

$$r = r_d + \overbrace{c_a \theta_a^{p_a}}^{r_a} + \overbrace{c_c \theta_c^{p_c}}^{r_c} \quad (3)$$

where θ_a and θ_c are the adsorbed and capillary volumetric water contents, r is the total transformed reflectance partitioned into three components of r_d , r_a , and r_c corresponding to the dry soil, adsorbed water, and capillary water, respectively, c_a and c_c are the ratios of water absorption to soil scattering for adsorbed and capillary water, respectively, p_a and p_c are two shape factors for the proposed nonlinear model. Eq. (3) with four fitting parameters (p_a , p_c , c_a , c_c) directly links the soil reflectance to soil hydraulic properties as explained below. Detailed information about the derivation of Eq. (3) is provided in Norouzi et al. (2022).

The Lebeau and Konrad (2010) model, hereafter termed LK model, is used to partition the total volumetric water content, θ , into the capillary and adsorbed components:

$$\theta = \theta_c + \theta_a \quad (4)$$

where the capillary component (θ_c) is modeled based on the Kosugi (1996) two-parameter model with zero residual water content and the adsorptive component (θ_a) is expressed as an inverse linear averaging of the Campbell and Shiozawa (1992) model for very low matric potentials (i.e., the region governed by adsorbed water) and the capillary component:

$$\theta_c = \frac{1}{2} \theta_s \operatorname{erfc} \left[\frac{\ln(h/h_m)}{\sqrt{2} \sigma} \right] \quad (5)$$

$$\theta_a = \left(1 - \frac{\theta_c}{\theta_s} \right) \theta_{camp} \quad (6)$$

where θ_s [m^3/m^3] is the saturated volumetric water content, h [m] is the matric potential, h_m [m] is the matric potential that corresponds to the median capillary pore radius, σ [-] is the standard deviation of the

Fig. 1. Flowchart of the applied optimization process.

log-transformed capillary pore radius distribution, $\text{erfc}()$ is the complementary error function, and θ_{camp} is the semilogarithmic expression proposed by Campbell and Shiozawa (1992) which represents the water content adsorbed on soil surfaces at very low matric potentials and is expressed as:

$$\theta_{camp} = \theta_o \left(1 - \frac{\ln|h|}{c} \right) \quad (7)$$

where θ_o [m^3/m^{-3}] is a curve-fitting parameter, and c is a universal constant related to the matric potential at oven dryness ($c = \ln|h_{dry}| = \ln|-10^5| = 11.51$) (Campbell and Shiozawa, 1992).

A more convenient and practical algorithm can be obtained when rewriting Eqs. (5) and (7) based on $\ln|h|$:

$$\ln|h| = \ln|h_m| + \sqrt{2}\sigma \text{erfc}^{-1}\left(2\frac{\theta_c}{\theta_s}\right) \quad (8)$$

$$\ln|h| = c - c\frac{\theta_{camp}}{\theta_o} \quad (9)$$

The variable h can be dropped by equating Eqs. (8) and (9):

$$\theta_{camp} = \theta_o - \frac{\theta_o}{c} \ln|h_m| - \sqrt{2}\sigma \frac{\theta_o}{c} \text{erfc}^{-1}\left(2\frac{\theta_c}{\theta_s}\right) \quad (10)$$

Eq. (10) can be combined with Eq. (6):

$$\theta_a = \left(1 - \frac{\theta_c}{\theta_s} \right) \left[\theta_o - \frac{\theta_o}{c} \ln|h_m| - \sqrt{2}\sigma \frac{\theta_o}{c} \text{erfc}^{-1}\left(2\frac{\theta_c}{\theta_s}\right) \right] \quad (11)$$

While the LK model has three free parameters [i.e., θ_o , h_m , σ], the partitioning of capillary and adsorbed water components may be incorporated via the two combined parameters A and B that are defined as:

$$\theta_a = \left(1 - \frac{\theta_c}{\theta_s} \right) \left[A + B \text{erfc}^{-1}\left(2\frac{\theta_c}{\theta_s}\right) \right] \quad (12a)$$

$$A = \theta_o - \frac{\theta_o}{c} \ln|h_m| \quad (12b)$$

$$B = -\sqrt{2}\sigma \frac{\theta_o}{c} \quad (12c)$$

Eqs. (5) and (12) combined with Eq. (3) directly connect the soil transformed reflectance, r , to the soil water retention curve parameters, θ_o , h_m and σ .

Recently, Norouzi et al. (2022) validated the proposed radiative transfer model [Eq. (3)] for 21 Arizona soils in a forward mode (i.e., estimating reflectance from the SWRC). In summary, they assumed that the SWRCs are known over a wide range of matric potentials and fitted the LK model directly to the measured SWRCs to partition the total water content into its components (θ_a and θ_c). The partitioned water content components were then substituted into Eq. (3) to establish the water content-reflectance relationship and study the optical model coefficients (p_a , p_c , c_a , c_c) within the SWIR bands (1300–2500 nm). The results indicate that the powers of the proposed model (p_a and p_c) are nearly independent of wavelength but rather depend on soil texture and mineralogy, while the spectrum of the dimensionless coefficients (c_a and c_c) has a similar shape as the water absorption spectrum for various soils with the baselines shifted vertically due to the difference in the scattering coefficient of the underlying soil.

In this study, we propose an inverse method for simultaneous estimation of the SWRC parameters (θ_o , h_m , σ) and the radiative transfer model parameters [p_a , p_c , c_a , c_c in Eq. (3)] from water content dependent SWIR reflectance data. We apply a constrained global search algorithm (Ugray et al., 2007) to invert Eq. (3) based on a priori knowledge about wavelength invariance of p_a and p_c gained from the application of the radiative transfer model in the forward mode. The interrelations between the SWRC parameters used to set the optimization constraints for the inverse method will be discussed in the following sections.

A flowchart illustrating the optimization process is depicted in Fig. 1. The optimization steps can be summarized as follows: (i) initial values are guessed for parameters that are independent of wavelength, including θ_o , h_m , σ , p_a and p_c ; (ii) if the SWRC parameters fall within the optimization constraints, the soil water content is partitioned into the capillary and adsorbed components (θ_a , θ_c), otherwise, the initial guesses are updated; (iii) Eq. (3) is fitted to the measurements at each SWIR wavelength via perturbing the wavelength-dependent coefficients c_a and c_c to minimize the RMSE between measured and estimated r - θ

Table 1
Textural properties of the Arizona soils studied.

Soil ID	Textural Class	Sand [%]	Silt [%]	Clay [%]	OM [%]	BD [g cm ⁻³]
AZ1	Sand	90.7	6.9	2.4	1.0	1.65
AZ2	Sand	96.3	3.1	0.6	0.9	1.64
AZ3	Loamy Sand	80.8	13.9	5.3	1.5	1.59
AZ4A	Sandy Loam	73.7	17.5	8.8	1.6	1.58
AZ4B	Loamy Sand	80.4	14.2	5.4	2.3	1.61
AZ5	Sandy Loam	67.0	24.5	8.5	2.6	1.60
AZ6	Sandy Loam	70.5	15.7	13.8	0.8	1.56
AZ7	Sandy Loam	58.5	32.0	9.5	1.1	1.50
AZ8	Sandy Clay	52.9	26.1	21.0	3.8	1.51
AZ9	Silt Loam	22.1	53.3	24.6	0.8	1.39
AZ10	Loam	37.4	45.9	16.7	3.5	1.40
AZ11	Loam	38.6	40.1	21.3	1.7	1.51
AZ12	Sandy Loam	66.0	14.5	19.5	0.5	1.57
AZ13	Sandy Clay	58.1	15.4	26.5	2.8	1.49
AZ14	Sandy Clay	51.4	21.6	27.0	1.5	1.48
AZ15	Silt Loam	3.6	73.4	23.0	3.4	1.27
AZ16	Clay Loam	25.6	45.2	29.2	3.4	1.31
AZ17	Silty Clay	9.3	40.2	50.5	1.3	1.27
AZ18	Clay	29.1	18.7	52.2	4.0	1.43
AZ19	Sandy Clay	48.9	20.8	30.3	2.3	1.51
AZ20	Sandy Loam	70.8	19.9	9.3	1.7	1.57

pairs; and (iv) the overall RMSE is calculated across all SWIR wavelengths and the previous steps are repeated until the least RMSE is achieved.

3. Experimental data

To test the proposed new laboratory method, we used 21 Arizona soils that vastly differ in texture (Table 1) and mineralogical composition (i.e., kaolinite, mica/illite, smectite, vermiculite, chlorite, and biotite contents). A description of the experimentally determined SWRCs and the reflectance spectra of the drying soils is provided below.

3.1. Soil water retention

Tempe cells (Soil moisture Equipment Corp., Santa Barbara, CA, USA) were used to measure the wet region of the SWRC. After air-drying the soil samples, they were passed through a 2-mm sieve. The Cosby et al. (1984) relationship $\theta_s = -0.126 \times \text{Sand}[\%] + 48.9$, was employed to estimate the dry bulk density, which was subsequently used to determine the soil mass required for packing the 70 cm³ Tempe cells and the shallow containers used to measure the reflectance spectra as a function of water content (section 3.3).

The Tempe cells on top of a saturated 1-bar ceramic plate were then slowly saturated with a constant head device (i.e., Mariotte's bottle). The saturated samples were then sequentially drained at matric potentials corresponding to super-atmospheric pressures of 0.5, 1.5, 3.0, 5.0, 10.0, 15.0, 50.0 and 80.0 kPa and the sample mass was recorded after each drainage step after the samples reached equilibrium. After completion of all drainage steps, the samples were oven-dried at 105 °C, and the gravimetric water contents corresponding to each drainage step were calculated. The dry bulk density was then used to convert from gravimetric to volumetric water contents.

A WP4-T Dewpoint Potentiometer (METER Group, Inc., Pullman, WA, USA), capable of measuring matric potentials between -0.1 MPa and -300 MPa was used to measure the dry region of the SWRC. This instrument applies a chilled mirror dewpoint technique to measure the relative humidity (RH) of soil air, which is considered to be in equilibrium with the soil water phase. The Kelvin equation is applied to convert RH to matric potential. To determine the gravimetric water content, the

Fig. 2. (a) The soil water retention model with capillary and adsorbed water contributions for a hypothetical soil with $\theta_0 = 0.18$, $\log|h_m| = 0.7$ and $\sigma = 1.3$. (b) Capillary and adsorbed water components that comprise the total soil water content.

soil samples were oven-dried at 105 °C. The dry bulk density was then used to convert from gravimetric to volumetric water contents. Three weeks prior to the measurements, five subsamples of each soil were brought to different water content levels that represent the dry region of the SWRC and stored in a refrigerator at 4 °C to allow equilibration prior to the measurements.

3.2. Soil texture and organic matter

A state-of-the-art Beckman Coulter LS 13320 laser diffraction particle size analyzer (Beckman Coulter Life Sciences, Indianapolis, IN, USA) was used to measure the soil texture (i.e., the sand, silt, and clay fractions). The instrument comprises of two laser systems, a standard system that covers the particle size range from 4.0E-04 to 2 mm, and a polarization intensity differential scattering (PIDS) system that extends down to 4.0E-05 mm while still providing a continuous size distribution. Because it is essential to measure the size distribution of primary mineral particles smaller than 2 mm calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) that acts as a binding agent and organic matter (OM) were removed prior to the measurements.

Soil organic carbon (SOC) was measured with a vario MACRO cube organic elemental analyzer (Elementar Analysensysteme GmbH, Langenselbold, Germany), and the SOC content was converted to OM content using a conversion factor of 2.0 (Pribyl, 2010).

3.3. Spectral reflectance

Reflectance spectra of the soils for various water content levels were measured with an ASD LabSpec®2500 spectroradiometer (Malvern Panalytical, Westborough, MA, USA). The spectra were acquired in the

Fig. 3. Variations of the Lebeau and Konrad (2010) model parameters and corresponding effects on the soil water retention curve (top row), the adsorbed water component (center row) and the capillary water component (bottom row). In each plot the other two parameters are kept constant and equal to the reference values in Fig. 2.

solar domain (350–2500 nm) with an illumination angle of 12° and a view angle of 34°. Oven-dry soil samples were passed through a 2-mm sieve and then packed into black metal containers with a diameter of 40 mm and a height of 1.5 mm. The same target packing densities as used for the SWRC measurements were considered for the reflectance measurements. The samples were carefully leveled (i.e., without compaction to minimize shadow effects). The soil samples were initially saturated with a 2-ml syringe and the reflectance spectra were acquired automatically every 3 min during soil drying from saturation to air-dry. The air-dry reflectance is used as the first component on the right-hand side of Eq. (3).

The volumetric soil water content corresponding to each spectrum was calculated as $\theta = BD(m_w - m_d)/m_d$, where BD is the soil bulk den-

sity, m_w is the wet soil mass, and m_d is the dry soil mass. To avoid errors in estimating soil water content, thin soil samples were chosen for the experiment. Thicker samples could have introduced discrepancies between surface soil water content (measured via reflectance spectra) and average soil water content (measured with a digital scale) (Philpot, 2014). Note that a sample thickness of 1.5 mm is adequate because it is likely greater than the light penetration depth for the dry AZ soils (i.e., approximately 1 mm) as shown in Norouzi et al. (2021).

4. Results

Typically, SWRC is highly nonlinear and because the matric potential extends over several orders of magnitude for the range of water contents commonly encountered in practical applications, the matric potential is plotted on a logarithmic scale (Tuller and Or, 2005). Fig. 2a illustrates the LK soil water retention model for a hypothetical soil with an arbitrary set of parameters (θ_0 , h_m and σ) along with capillary and adsorbed water components. The capillary component follows a sigmoidal shape in the wet range, and the adsorptive component exhibits logarithmic behavior in the dry range. The capillary and adsorbed water-dominant regions of the SWRCs are separated by the water content at which the capillary and adsorbed water curves intersect. The contributions depicted in Fig. 2a should be considered as follows: for a given matric potential, h , the corresponding water content value (black line denoted as “SWRC”) is the sum of the capillary and adsorptive components.

Once the parameters of the LK model are determined, the capillary and adsorbed water contributions can be calculated as a fraction of the total water content. This partitioning is shown in Fig. 2b, which provides a critical input for the proposed reflectance model, Eq. (3). As shown in Fig. 2b, capillary and adsorbed water coexist above the transition point, while below the transition point soil water is entirely made up of the adsorbed component. From a physical standpoint, this is consistent with the faster decline of the capillary water than the adsorbed water as the soil dries out [see Fig. 1 of Norouzi et al. (2022)].

Fig. 4. Best fit of the Lebeau and Konrad (2010) model to the measured soil water retention curve data for four AZ soils with different clay contents.

Fig. 5. Correlation of the best-fit A and B parameters (left) and the optimization bounds used for inverse parameter estimation (right). A and B represent the combined coefficients in Eq. (12).

To establish an efficient inversion algorithm, we studied the sensitivity of the SWRC and water content components with regard to the LK model parameters. We considered the soil in Fig. 2 and changed the LK parameters one at a time, while keeping the other parameters constant. Fig. 3 shows the results of this analysis. As observed, changing θ_o has a

distinct effect on the dry region of the SWRC. The parameter θ_o is the main parameter in the equation proposed by Campbell and Shiozawa (1992) for the dry end of the SWRC [Eq. (7)] and also the sole parameter shared between the combined parameters that determine the partitioning [i.e., A and B in Eq. (12)]. Increasing θ_o shifts the peak of the

Fig. 6. (a) Measured transformed reflectance versus soil water content for AZ3 (loamy sand) and AZ18 (clay) soils for different shortwave infrared bands. (b) First derivative of transformed reflectance with respect to water content (solid lines) and their corresponding global maxima (open circles). (c) Water contents associated with the global $dr/d\theta$ maxima plotted as density distributions (Eilers and Goeman, 2004) for all SWIR wavelengths versus adsorbed and capillary water components.

adsorbed water component toward higher water contents. A similar effect can be observed for the capillary water component. The parameter h_m also moves the base of the SWRC vertically and causes the water components to shift toward left and right. The parameter σ only affects the transition from the wet to dry end. This parameter has a negligible effect on the curvature of the water components without significantly affecting the transition point. Therefore, this parameter is expected to be related to the powers of the radiative transfer model [Eq. (3)].

Fig. 4 illustrates the best fit of the LK model to the measured SWRC data of four example Arizona soils with vastly different clay contents. Results for all 21 Arizona soils are presented in Norouzi et al. (2022). As observed, the LK model yields a close fit to the measured values, especially in the dry region, where classical capillarity-based models often perform poorly. In our sensitivity analysis in Fig. 3, we changed the LK parameters one by one and kept the remaining parameters constant. However, it is evident in Fig. 4 that the LK parameters are interrelated. For example, as the clay percentage increases, all three model parameters (θ_o , $|h_m|$, and σ) increase. In other words, soils with higher θ_o values are expected to have higher $|h_m|$ and σ values. This interrelation between the coefficients enables streamlining the inverse determination of model parameters as explained below.

It should be noted that the LK model assigns a constant value of $h = -10^5$ m to the matric potential at the hypothetical zero water content [matric potential at oven dryness, see Eq. (7)]. Although zero water content does not exist in either theory or practice, it is considered in several models studying the dry-end of the SWRC and its value has been shown to be variable and a function of clay mineralogy (Karup et al., 2017; Lu and Khorshidi, 2015).

The interrelation between the SWRC parameters shown in Fig. 5 for all Arizona soils was used to establish the constraints for the optimization process (Fig. 1). Utilizing constraints enables streamlining the space of acceptable solutions and obtaining a unique set of SWRC parameters. No soil-specific information was required to set the constraints, and invariant constraints were applied for all investigated soils (i.e., solid lines in Fig. 5). The values depicted in Fig. 5 are for the best-fit for all investigated soils, and the constraint lines were chosen to enclose all the data points.

Fig. 6a depicts the measured transformed reflectance plotted against total water content for three SWIR bands for the AZ3 (loamy sand) and AZ18 (clay) soils, which are at the extreme ends of the investigated soil textures. The r - θ curves of each soil at different wavelengths are similar in shape, but they differ in the magnitude of r due to the strong water absorptivity within the SWIR region (Kou et al., 1993). The first derivative of transformed reflectance with respect to total water content, $dr/d\theta$, better illustrates this shape similarity as shown in Fig. 6b. The derivatives exhibit similar patterns, which affirms that the powers of the radiative transfer model (p_a, p_c) are independent of wavelength and can be considered as constant soil properties. This reduces the uncertainty associated with the inversion of the SWRC parameters.

Another important feature visualized in Fig. 6b is the point at which the global maximum of $dr/d\theta$ occurs, which implies a distinct change in the reflective properties of water at the soil surface. To better comprehend this point, the water contents at which this global maximum happens were extracted for all wavelengths within the range from 900 to 2500 nm and plotted together with their density distributions (Fig. 6c). As observed, the location of the global maximum is nearly fixed in the SWIR range (1400–2500 nm) for both soils. In addition, this point is substantially different for these two extreme soils. The plot of water content components on the right axis reveals that this location marks the water content at which the adsorbed water reaches its maximum. This reaffirms our postulation that soil reflectance spectra encompass rich information about soil hydraulic properties.

Fig. 6c also indicates that for wavelengths smaller than 1400 nm the water contents associated with the global $dr/d\theta$ maxima shift to smaller values of about $0.15 \text{ [m}^3/\text{m}^3\text{]}$ for the AZ18 soil. This is because of the

Table 2

The soil water retention parameters for the studied AZ soils retrieved using the proposed method.

Soil ID	$\theta_o \text{ [m}^3/\text{m}^3\text{]}$	$h_m \text{ [m]}$	$\sigma \text{ [-]}$	$A \text{ [m}^3/\text{m}^3\text{]}$	$B \text{ [m}^3/\text{m}^3\text{]}$
AZ1	0.08	0.51	1.24	0.085	-0.012
AZ2	0.10	0.85	1.57	0.101	-0.019
AZ3	0.09	0.90	1.04	0.091	-0.011
AZ4A	0.10	1.26	1.16	0.098	-0.014
AZ4B	0.10	1.59	1.39	0.096	-0.017
AZ5	0.14	3.06	1.86	0.126	-0.032
AZ6	0.16	1.32	1.20	0.156	-0.024
AZ7	0.19	1.01	1.54	0.190	-0.036
AZ8	0.11	1.54	1.46	0.106	-0.020
AZ9	0.26	1.01	1.40	0.260	-0.045
AZ10	0.14	1.03	1.39	0.140	-0.024
AZ11	0.24	1.60	1.67	0.230	-0.049
AZ12	0.22	1.48	1.60	0.213	-0.043
AZ13	0.20	2.04	1.95	0.188	-0.048
AZ14	0.19	0.89	0.79	0.192	-0.018
AZ15	0.29	1.67	2.00	0.277	-0.071
AZ16	0.20	2.10	1.10	0.187	-0.027
AZ17	0.35	7.02	1.40	0.291	-0.060
AZ18	0.28	0.84	1.69	0.284	-0.058
AZ19	0.25	1.25	1.29	0.245	-0.040
AZ20	0.10	1.48	1.28	0.097	-0.016

substantially smaller water absorptivity at these wavelengths, which causes other interferences to exceed the effect of water on reflectance. Hence, for the inverse estimation of SWRC parameters we only considered wavelengths from 1400 to 2500 nm, where the sensitivity of reflectance to soil water content is highest (Eon and Bachmann, 2021).

Table 2 lists the optimized SWRC parameters for the 21 investigated soils. It should be noted that Table 2 presents the absolute values of h_m . The retrieved capillary and adsorbed components of the total water content are depicted in Fig. 7 in comparison with the corresponding components from the least-square fitting of the LK model to the measured SWRC data. As observed, the partitioning varies considerably across different soil types. These results confirm that capillary and adsorbed water coexist above the transition point, whereas adsorbed water is dominant below the transition point. From a physics perspective, this is due to the faster decline of capillary water than adsorbed water during soil drying. Furthermore, for finer soil textures with higher clay content, the peak of the adsorbed water component shifts towards the higher values. This texture-dependent behavior of the water components was effectively captured in the results obtained through the proposed inversion method. This highlights the wealth of information present in the water content-dependent reflectance spectra with regard to soil physical and hydraulic properties.

Fig. 8 shows the retrieved SWRCs using the proposed inversion method in comparison with the measured SWRC data pairs. The SWRCs retrieved from SWIR reflectance are in good agreement with the direct measurements. The uncertainty of the retrieved SWRCs in Fig. 8 is slightly higher than the uncertainty observed for the retrievals of soil water content components (Fig. 7). For example, while the retrieved capillary and adsorbed soil water components of the AZ1 and AZ10 soils closely match the corresponding components derived via direct fitting (Fig. 7), their corresponding retrieved SWRCs slightly deviate from the measured data (Fig. 8). This can be anticipated, because the proposed SWRC model consists of three free parameters (θ_o, h_m, σ), while partitioning of capillary and adsorbed water components is controlled by two combined coefficients in Eq. (12) ($A = \theta_o - \frac{\theta_o}{c} \ln|h_m|, B = -\sqrt{2}\sigma\frac{\theta_o}{c}$).

The correlation between water contents derived with the proposed new method from SWIR reflectance and directly measured values are depicted in Fig. 9. The estimations obtained from the new method are in good agreement with the measurements. The performance of the new inverse method is less accurate for intermediate water contents than the water contents at the dry and wet ends.

Fig. 7. Capillary and adsorbed water components obtained with the proposed inverse method compared to the corresponding components obtained from the best fit of Lebeau and Konrad (2010) model to the measured soil water retention curves of the 21 AZ soils.

Fig. 8. SWRCs for the 21 considered AZ soils retrieved with the new proposed model compared to direct measurements.

Fig. 9. Comparison between the soil water contents obtained from shortwave infrared reflectance using the new laboratory method and the directly measured values for all investigated soils.

5. Discussion

As shown in Table 2, the parameter θ_o , which determines the slope of SWRC in a semi-logarithmic space near the dry end, obtained higher values for fine-textured soils. This observation is consistent with the previous findings of Lebeau and Konrad (2010), as presented in Table 2 of their study. Furthermore, the results of Campbell and Shiozawa (1992) showed a notable positive correlation between θ_o and the clay content.

A similar connection, albeit inverse, can be discerned between the parameter h_m and the clay content. The parameter h_m represents the matric potential associated with the median capillary pore radius. Consequently, according to the Young-Laplace equation, soils with smaller median pore sizes (i.e., fine-textured soils) are expected to have lower h_m values (i.e., more negative).

As shown in Table 2, no distinct relation can be observed between the parameter σ and the soil texture. The sensitivity analysis presented in Fig. 3 demonstrates that this parameter exerts a negligible influence on the distribution of capillary and adsorbed soil water components. Consequently, its retrieval is associated with a higher degree of uncertainty when compared to the retrieval of the other two LK model parameters.

Several factors may contribute to the discrepancies observed between the retrieved and measured SWRCs in Fig. 8. First, while the 70 cm³ cylindrical Tempe cells (see Section 3.1) can be accurately packed to a predefined bulk density (BD), it is rather challenging to obtain the exact same target BD values for the thin soil samples used for reflectance measurements. Because the SWRC is strongly affected by BD it is often used as an input variable for SWRC pedotransfer functions (Schaap et al., 2001; Vereecken et al., 2010). In addition, assuming that gravimetric water content is the same, BD affects the volumetric water content (Assouline, 2006).

Second, the LK model, which is at the core of the current radiative transfer model [Eq. (3)], has been developed based on several simplifying assumptions which could be violated in reality. Parametric SWRC models, including the LK model, were developed based on the postulation that the empirical expression of Campbell and Shiozawa (1992) [Eq. (7)] for the very dry end of SWRC can be also applied to wetter regions as a linearly decreasing function of the capillary component to yield the total adsorbed water component over the entire saturation range [Eq.

(3)]. However, experimental evidence and thermodynamic considerations for water retention in angular pores reveal a much more complex transition from capillary- to adsorbed water-dominated system states applicable at both the pore and sample scales (Tuller et al., 1999; Tuller and Or, 2001; Nishiyama and Yokoyama, 2021).

Finally, the assumption of a constant value for matric potential at the hypothetical zero water content reduces the flexibility of the LK model in accurately matching the measured SWRC, especially for coarse-textured soils (e.g., AZ1 in Fig. 4), and consequently induces potential deviations of the proposed model with actual observations.

As depicted in Fig. 9, the deviations between the retrieved and measured water contents are more pronounced within the intermediate range. Based on the sensitivity analysis shown in Fig. 3, the transition from the wet end of SWRC to the dry end is mainly determined by the parameter σ . As discussed above, the retrieval of this parameter is more uncertain than the other two LK parameters and this could be one reason for the observed deviations in intermediate water content range in Fig. 9.

Current physics-based models for the retrieval of water retention curve parameters rely on the inversion of the highly nonlinear Richards' water flow equation as shown, for example, in Babaeian et al. (2021) and Yu et al. (2021). In contrast, the proposed new laboratory method directly derives soil retention curve parameters from soil reflectance spectra. This direct link significantly reduces the mathematical complexity and consequently minimizes the uncertainty associated with model inversion. In addition, reflectance spectra of a drying soil sample can be acquired much faster and with a less complex laboratory setup than used for other existing methods.

6. Conclusions

A new physics-based laboratory method that enables retrieval of the soil water retention curve (SWRC) directly from soil water content-SWIR reflectance data pairs was introduced. The obtained results provide strong support for our hypothesis that there is a significant difference in the optical properties of the capillary and adsorbed water components of the SWRC due to their distinct distribution within the soil pore system. This difference is key to the successful SWRC retrievals from water content dependent reflectance data.

Considering that the shortwave infrared (SWIR) reflectance of a

drying thin soil sample from saturation to air-dry can be measured within a few hours, the proposed new method is highly time-efficient when compared to the standard laboratory methods which often take several weeks. At the expense of computational efficiency, constraining the proposed inversion method by Richards' equation may potentially increase the accuracy of the SWRC retrievals. This is part of our ongoing research.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Sarem Norouzi: Conceptualization, Methodology, Data curation, Formal analysis, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Morteza Sadeghi:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Data curation, Writing – review & editing. **Markus Tuller:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Data curation, Visualization, Resources, Writing – review & editing. **Hamed Ebrahimi:** Writing – review & editing. **Abdolmajid Liaghat:** Writing – review & editing. **Scott B. Jones:** Resources, Writing – review & editing. **Lis W. de Jonge:** Supervision, Resources, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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